

Coordinated Jamming and Poisoning Attack Detection and Mitigation in Wireless Federated Learning Networks

SOFIA BARKATSA¹, MARIA DIAMANTI¹ (Member, IEEE),
PANAGIOTIS CHARATSARIS¹ (Graduate Student Member, IEEE), STEFANOS VOIKOS¹,
EIRINI ELENI TSIROPOULOU² (Senior Member, IEEE),
AND SYMEON PAPAVALASSIOU¹ (Senior Member, IEEE)

(Special Issue on Trustworthy AI-Enabled Edge Computing in Next-Generation Wireless Networks)

¹Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 15780 Zografou, Greece

²Performance and Resource Optimization in Networks – PROTON Lab, School of Electrical, Computer and Energy Engineering, Arizona State University, Tempe, AZ 85287, USA

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: M. DIAMANTI (e-mail: mdiamanti@netmode.ntua.gr)

This work was supported in part by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe/JU SNS Project Hexa-X-II under Grant 101095759.

ABSTRACT Wireless Federated Learning (FL) is a distributed Artificial Intelligence (AI) framework, enabling decision-making at the network edge where data are generated. However, wireless transmissions of model updates from edge nodes to the coordinating server are vulnerable to jamming, alongside the inherent risk of poisoning the learning process. In this paper, we tackle the problem of coordinated jamming and poisoning attacks in wireless FL networks, where malicious edge nodes disrupt transmissions of legitimate local model updates to the cloud server while injecting poisoned model updates to manipulate the global model. To this end, we introduce two complementary mechanisms operating alternately. First, a robust global model aggregation algorithm is developed to address poisoning attacks by weighting edge nodes' local model updates using a novel contribution index. The calculation of the index is inspired by the Shapley value, but it offers polynomial complexity compared to existing methods. Subsequently, a distributed power control solution for jamming attack mitigation in the uplink of the FL network is introduced based on Bayesian games with incomplete information. Both legitimate and malicious nodes aim to successfully transmit their model parameters, minimizing transmission power and time to the server, while having probabilistic knowledge about the malicious behavior of the other nodes in the game. The proposed unified approach and each individual mechanism are assessed via modeling and simulation, verifying their effectiveness in mitigating both attacks while achieving a good tradeoff between global model accuracy and consumed time and energy compared to state-of-the-art approaches.

INDEX TERMS Bayesian games, contribution averaging, federated learning, incomplete information, jamming, poisoning, power control, robust aggregation.

I. INTRODUCTION

WIRELESS Federated Learning (FL) has emerged as an architectural paradigm in the direction of distributed Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native support in 6G networks [1]. Especially when blending edge computing resources with AI techniques, wireless FL allows processing and decision-making exactly at the point where data are generated. This

reduces latency and improves real-time responsiveness for advanced AI applications (e.g., vehicle-to-everything communications [2], trajectory planning [3], AI-based offloading [4]) while preserving local data privacy. Distributed edge nodes seamlessly handle decision-making by exchanging local model parameters with a server in the cloud, where global consensus is established. However, as wireless FL gains importance and

finds applications across diverse fields in the 6G era, it brings its own trustworthiness issues that must be addressed [5], [6].

FL introduces vulnerabilities in the learning process as a distributed learning technique while the wireless communication aspect further compromises model integrity by adding a new attack surface. Among the potential risks associated with the learning process, poisoning attacks represent one of the most critical threats. Malicious edge nodes may deliberately provide unreliable local model updates to the cloud by training on biased or corrupted local data, mislabeling the training data, or altering the objective of local training [7]. The impact of a poisoning attack in wireless FL networks is exacerbated when combined with network-related attacks that aim to prevent legitimate edge nodes from transmitting or receiving updated local model parameters from the cloud. Under a jamming attack, legitimate edge nodes are subjected to excessive interference, altering channel conditions and complicating signal detection and interference cancellation at the cloud server [8]. In a coordinated attack scenario, fewer legitimate nodes transmit their local models successfully to the cloud server, which amplifies the influence of poisoned local updates upon aggregation. Consequently, by adjusting both poisoned local updates and the transmission power level, a malicious node can enhance its detrimental impact on the cloud server's global model.

In this paper, we strive to address the issue of coordinated jamming and poisoning attacks in wireless FL networks. Unlike existing research that focuses separately on poisoning and network-related attacks in wireless FL, we introduce a unified approach to concurrently ensure efficient communication and preserve global model accuracy. Our approach integrates two complementary mechanisms: (i) a robust global model aggregation algorithm to mitigate poisoning attacks and (ii) an adaptive power control strategy to counter jamming attacks. First, we develop a novel index inspired by the Shapley value to assess each edge node's contribution to the global model, used as a weight to dynamically update the global model. The resulting global model aggregation algorithm effectively balances efficiency in poisoning attack detection and mitigation while maintaining linear complexity, making it practical for application in realistic large-scale FL networks. For anti-jamming power control, we formulate a non-cooperative Bayesian game with incomplete information between the legitimate and malicious edge nodes. Each node autonomously selects its uplink transmission power to ensure the successful transmission of local model parameters to the cloud while minimizing the induced transmission power and time. The game considers the inherent uncertainty about the nodes' type of malice (i.e., malicious or legitimate), presenting another major difference from existing works unilaterally treating jamming attacks in wireless FL.

A. RELATED WORK

Security in FL networks is generally a critical and increasingly studied topic, with several systematic reviews on the types of adversaries and the associated countermeasures [7].

Remarkably, a large body of literature is devoted to developing node selection mechanisms that enhance robustness against attacks, while addressing key metrics such as resource and communication efficiency, scalability, and non-IID data, e.g., [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. Strategies to sequentially eliminate misbehaving nodes, like stragglers, dropouts, and malicious, have been developed based on reputation threshold values, e.g., [9]. The uncertainty behind the nodes' misbehavior has also been considered in [10] during node selection via a stochastic integer programming optimization method. Furthermore, dynamic adaptation of the respective reputation threshold has been proposed in [11] to detect and remove unreliable nodes in each FL round efficiently. In addition to assessing the reliability of edge nodes based on their contributions to the global model, node selection schemes have been developed to address unreliable traffic data caused by Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks [12], which aim to disrupt the convergence of the FL process. Other works, e.g., [13], [14], optimize node selection and resource allocation to reduce data errors and misalignments during local model transmissions due to wireless channel quality and interference.

Nevertheless, node selection mechanisms may compromise fairness by utilizing contributions from only a limited number of nodes, which issue is particularly pronounced in cross-silo FL settings [15], where the number of participating nodes is inherently small. To this end, robust aggregation methods [16] present a promising alternative for estimating the global model parameters while mitigating the effect of malicious updates. These methods include the geometric median, trimmed median, median [16], [17] and Krum [18] estimators, while more advanced implementations based on model statistics have been explored, including but not limited to the works in [15], [19]. All aforementioned robust aggregation methods effectively handle corrupted model updates due to operational failures or malicious behavior but lack robustness guarantees when local datasets are imbalanced or heterogeneous. In this regard, other commonly employed model aggregation strategies often assign weights to the local model parameters of different nodes [15]. A well-known solution for calculating representative weights is the Shapley value, inherited from cooperative game theory. It represents a node's weighted average of marginal contributions, i.e., the utility differences between node sets with and without the specific node [20]. In particular, the works in [21], [22] propose model aggregation methods based on the Shapley value. Since calculating the complexity of the Shapley value for each node in a network of N nodes is $\mathcal{O}(2^N)$, both works focus on efficient polynomial-time approximations.

Interestingly, while an extensive body of literature addresses poisoning attacks in FL networks, research on network-related attacks remains comparatively limited. The two most studied network attacks in wireless FL networks are eavesdropping and jamming. The research on eavesdropping mainly focuses on designing efficient artificial jamming strategies to intentionally interfere with

the eavesdropper [23], [24], [25]. Artificial jamming can be cooperatively performed by the distributed nodes when a certain node transmits its local model parameters to the FL server [23], [26]. Other works focus on convert wireless FL architectures by leveraging the flexibility and maneuverability of Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to provide artificial jamming to the underlying FL network [24], [25]. Concerning jamming attacks, again a handful of works can be found [26], [27], [28], [29]. The impact of over-the-air jamming attacks in wireless FL networks is first quantified in [27], demonstrating that attacking a single node reduces the global model accuracy to 84.8% in uplink and to 63.1% in downlink attack scenarios. In more complex multi-hop wireless FL network settings, the authors in [28] design algorithms to identify the links to be jammed and the jammer positions, evaluating the impact on the convergence time and accuracy of the FL process. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the work in [29] is the only attempt to develop an anti-jamming power control strategy for wireless FL networks. Specifically, the problem of joint channel selection and power allocation among all distributed nodes in the network is formulated and solved as a Stackelberg game, with the jammer acting as the leader and the legitimate nodes as the followers.

Several other game-theoretic anti-jamming strategies can be found in the broader literature beyond FL networks, respecting the need for distributed resource allocation, e.g., [30], [31]. Game formulations vary from two-player stateless power control games [30] to coalition formation games [31], where network users form groups that share the same time-frequency resources to protect heavily jammed users through artificial jamming. Nevertheless, acquiring information about the type of user in a network – whether legitimate or malicious – is challenging and impractical in real deployments where there is no information exchange between the jammer and the rest of the users. Bayesian game formulations provide a prominent solution to this challenge by incorporating the incompleteness of information about the other players' types and actions in the decision-making process. Motivated by this property, the authors in [32] propose a one-leader one-follower Bayesian Stackelberg game between a jammer and a UAV offering communication services to determine their transmission powers under incomplete information about their transmission gains. A similar one-leader one-follower approach is followed in [33], where the jammer and the legitimate user determine their joint time and power-domain allocations.

B. CONTRIBUTIONS AND OUTLINE

In this paper, we aim to address the gap in the literature by jointly considering model and network-related attacks in wireless FL networks, with a particular emphasis on jamming attacks, which remain largely unexplored. To this end, we consider a wireless FL network where malicious nodes disrupt the successful transmission of local model parameters from legitimate nodes through jamming attacks

while simultaneously manipulating the global model through poisoned updates. To defend against coordinated jamming and poisoning attacks, this paper introduces a unified approach that includes two complementary mechanisms, which operate alternately to address both types of attacks. In more detail, the main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

- 1) The model and operation of a wireless FL network with malicious edge nodes are introduced, where coordinated jamming and poisoning attacks are launched.
- 2) A robust global model aggregation algorithm is devised for the cloud server to mitigate poisoning attacks by evaluating each node's contribution to the global model via a Shapley value-inspired index. Unlike existing approaches, this algorithm has linear complexity.
- 3) An anti-jamming power control solution is proposed as a Bayesian game with incomplete information between legitimate and malicious nodes that autonomously determine their power levels to successfully transmit their local models to the server and minimize the transmission power and time. The malicious nodes additionally seek to minimize the utility of the legitimate nodes. Unlike existing literature in the FL domain, which assumes complete knowledge of the adversarial behavior, this solution models the probabilistic uncertainty regarding the malice type of nodes.
- 4) Extensive numerical evaluation through modeling and simulation reveals the operational characteristics of coordinated jamming and poisoning attacks, and the effectiveness of the two mechanisms in global model accuracy, transmission power, and time. Both mechanisms are compared against state-of-the-art solutions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the FL and communication model of the wireless FL network are presented. Section III introduces the anti-poisoning contribution averaging algorithm and the convergence guarantees. Section IV introduces the anti-jamming power control based on Bayesian games with incomplete information. Section V provides a performance evaluation and results, and Section VI concludes the paper.

Notation: Vectors are indicated by bold-face letters. For any real-valued vector \mathbf{x} , $\|\mathbf{x}\|$ represents the Euclidean norm of \mathbf{x} . The transpose vector of \mathbf{x} is denoted by \mathbf{x}^\top . All sets are denoted using calligraphic letters, while their cardinalities are represented with regular letters. $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ is the statistical expectation and $\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$ is the big-O computational complexity notation.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a wireless FL network, where distributed edge nodes collaborate to train an AI model under the coordination of a server in the cloud. The FL network comprises a set of legitimate edge nodes, denoted by $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, n, \dots, N\}$, and a set of malicious edge nodes $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, m, \dots, M\}$ which launch coordinated jamming and poisoning attacks. On one hand, their objective is to interfere with the legitimate

nodes' uplink transmissions to prevent their contributions to the cloud server. On the other hand, as illustrated in Fig. 1, the malicious nodes receive global model updates from the server—similarly to legitimate nodes—and train their local models using poisoned data to harm the global model in subsequent FL rounds. To this end, the primary resources utilized by the malicious nodes for conducting coordinated attacks are their uplink transmission power levels and their poisoned local datasets. It should be noted that while this paper focuses on a holistic framework to tackle coordinated jamming and poisoning attacks, the modeling approach is modular and can also be independently applied to detect and mitigate either jamming or poisoning attacks in wireless FL networks.

A. FEDERATED LEARNING MODEL

Each node $i \in \mathcal{I} = \mathcal{N} \cup \mathcal{M}$ performs training of its local AI model with parameters \mathbf{w}_i^t during each communication round t , based on its local set of training data $\mathcal{D}_i = \{\mathbf{x}_j, y_j\}_{j=1}^{D_i}$ of cardinality D_i . Given that the FL process focuses on a classification problem, \mathbf{x}_j is the j -th input sample and y_j is the corresponding label. The total dataset of the network, comprising the samples from all nodes, is $\mathcal{D} = \bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \mathcal{D}_i = \{\mathbf{x}_j, y_j\}_{j=1}^D$, while the cloud server maintains its own separate dataset \mathcal{D}_s to monitor the local and global models' quality.

The model $\mathbf{w}_i^t, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$ in each round t is derived to minimize the local training loss F_i , expressed as

$$F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i^t) = \frac{1}{D_i} \sum_{j=1}^{D_i} f_i(\mathbf{x}_j, y_j, \mathbf{w}_i^t), \quad (1)$$

where f_i is the cross-entropy loss function [34] for a single sample j , representing the classification error. To minimize the classification error, each node performs λ local model updates via the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) with a learning rate $\eta \in (0, 1]$. The updated local model parameters between subsequent local model iterations are given by

$$\mathbf{w}_i^{t,l} = \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l-1} - \eta \nabla F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l-1}), \forall l \in [1, \dots, \lambda]. \quad (2)$$

Due to the jamming attacks, the local model parameters' of some legitimate nodes may fail to be successfully decoded at the server end. Let $\mathcal{S}^t \subseteq \mathcal{I}$ denote the set of nodes effectively contributing to the FL process in communication round t of cardinality S^t . Then, the updated local models $\mathbf{w}_i^t, \forall i \in \mathcal{S}^t$ are collected by the cloud server and the aggregated AI model for round t is generated using the Contribution Averaging (ContrAvg) FL algorithm, as outlined in Section III.

B. COMMUNICATION MODEL

In each communication round t , the local model parameters from the nodes are transmitted to the server over the same frequency resources of bandwidth B [Hz] using the power-domain Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) technique. Let G_i denote the channel gain between node $i \in \mathcal{I}$ and the server. Without loss of generality, we assume

FIGURE 1. Overview of the wireless FL network with malicious nodes executing coordinated jamming and poisoning attacks.

that the channel gains from nodes $i \in \mathcal{I}$ to the server are sorted in ascending order, such that $G_1 \leq G_2 \leq \dots \leq G_{N+M}$. Signal decoding starts at the node with the highest channel gain, utilizing the Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) technique. In the remainder of this section, we drop the index t associated with the communication rounds for notational simplicity.

The achieved data rate of each node $i \in \mathcal{I}$ is calculated as

$$R_i = B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{G_i p_i}{\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} G_j p_j + I_0 B} \right) [\text{bps}], \quad (3)$$

where p_i [Watt] denotes the uplink transmission power of edge node i and I_0 [dBm/Hz] represents the power spectral density of zero-mean Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN).

Accordingly, the time overhead experienced by node $i \in \mathcal{I}$ for transmitting its local model parameters to the server is

$$T_i = \frac{Z(\mathbf{w}_i)}{R_i} [\text{sec}], \quad (4)$$

where $Z(\mathbf{w}_i)$ [bits] is the size of the local model parameters vector \mathbf{w}_i . Also, the corresponding incurred energy overhead from the transmission is calculated as

$$E_i = \frac{Z(\mathbf{w}_i) \cdot p_i}{R_i} [\text{Joule}]. \quad (5)$$

To ensure the successful decoding of the edge nodes' local model parameter messages at the cloud server, the following condition should be met

$$p_i \tilde{G}_i - \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} p_j \tilde{G}_j \geq p_{tol} \Rightarrow p_i \geq \underbrace{\frac{\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} p_j \tilde{G}_j + p_{tol}}{\tilde{G}_i}}_{p_i^{thr}(\mathbf{p}_{-i})}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}, \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{G}_i = \frac{G_i}{I_0 B}$ is the normalized channel gain of edge node i and p_{tol} [dBm] is the receiver's sensitivity/tolerance. From Eq. (6), the minimum required transmission power p_i^{thr} for successful decoding is derived for each node as a function of the transmission powers of the rest of the nodes, i.e., $\mathbf{p}_{-i} = [p_0, \dots, p_{i-1}, p_{i+1}, \dots, p_{N+M}]$.

III. ANTI-POISONING CONTRIBUTION AVERAGING FL

In this section, we introduce a robust global model aggregation algorithm, termed Contribution Averaging (ContrAvg), to defend against poisoning attacks in wireless FL networks. First, a novel index is developed to evaluate each local model's contribution to the global model, followed by the design of the ContrAvg algorithm. The section is further complemented by the analysis of the FL process's convergence guarantee when using the ContrAvg algorithm.

A. CONTRIBUTION AVERAGING (CONTRAVG) ALGORITHM

As stated earlier, to detect and mitigate poisoning attacks in the wireless FL network, we calculate each node's marginal contribution to the global model and use it as a weight during aggregation. The method for quantifying the contribution is based on the Shapley value [20], a solution concept used in cooperative game theory to measure each player's contribution. Analytically, the Shapley value of a player is defined as the weighted average of its marginal contributions, which are derived as the difference in utility between sets with and without the specific player. By considering all possible cooperation scenarios, the Shapley value effectively distinguishes valuable players from malicious players. Thus, a Shapley-based index is well-suited to evaluate node contribution in FL. However, the Shapley value calculation is known to scale exponentially with the number of players/nodes, which can significantly increase the overhead of distributed learning processes like FL. To address this issue, in this paper, we aim to go beyond existing literature [21], [22], and introduce a novel Shapley-inspired contribution index with linear complexity, which significantly reduces computation time while performing closely to the original Shapley value.

To facilitate the subsequent analysis, consider a communication/FL round t and the set of nodes S^t whose transmitted local model parameters $\mathbf{w}_i^t, \forall i \in S^t$ have been successfully decoded by the server. Then, for any subset $C \subseteq S^t$ of nodes, the respective aggregated model created by the server is

$$\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_C^t = \sum_{i \in C} \frac{D_i}{\sum_{j \in C} D_j} \mathbf{w}_i^t. \quad (7)$$

Also, let $Q(\cdot)$ represent the function that produces as output the accuracy of a given model, such that $Q(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_C^t)$ represents the accuracy of the model $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_C^t$ created by the server. Note that to calculate the accuracy Q , the server utilizes its private local set of a limited number of IID samples $\mathcal{D}_{\text{server}}$, which can still provide an indicative measure of the quality of other trained models by individual nodes or subsets of nodes in the network.

Then, the calculation of the Shapley-inspired index in this paper is performed as follows. The server calculates for each node $i \in S^t$ its contribution index ϕ_i^t to the global model as (i) the difference in accuracy between sets S^t and $S^t - \{i\}$ with and without node i , i.e., $Q(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{S^t}^t) - Q(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{S^t - \{i\}}^t)$, and (ii) the difference in accuracy between node's i local model \mathbf{w}_i^t

and the aggregated global model from the previous FL round $t + 1$, i.e., $Q(\mathbf{w}_i^t) - Q(\mathbf{w}^{t-1})$. Therefore, the Shapley-inspired contribution index ϕ_i^t of edge node i at communication/FL round t is formally defined as

$$\phi_i^t = \kappa_1 \cdot \left(Q(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{S^t}^t) - Q(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{S^t - \{i\}}^t) \right) + \kappa_2 \cdot \left(Q(\mathbf{w}_i^t) - Q(\mathbf{w}^{t-1}) \right) \quad (8)$$

where $\kappa_1, \kappa_2 \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are constants used to scale the outcomes of the two terms in (8). The rationale behind the Shapley-inspired index in (8) is that only two comparisons suffice to provide a reliable estimate of the quality of a local model \mathbf{w}_i^t , in contrast to the 2^{S^t-1} comparisons needed by the original Shapley value in our setting. The first term in (8) indicates whether a node contributes positively to the construction of the global model compared to others. The second term in (8) evaluates whether a local model improves or degrades the aggregated global model from the previous round, especially in the case of a malicious node's local model that reduces the accuracy achieved in the previous FL round. This ensures the effective detection of poisoning attacks.

To guarantee that the contribution indices of all nodes in the set S^t are positive and sum up to one, the values of $\phi_i^t, \forall i \in S^t$ are passed to the Softmax function, which gives the final contribution score $a_i, \forall i \in S^t$ as follows

$$a_i^t = \frac{e^{\phi_i^t}}{\sum_{j \in S^t} e^{\phi_j^t}}. \quad (9)$$

After the server computes the contribution indices $a_i, \forall i \in S^t$ in FL round t , the final step entails determining the new aggregated global model for FL round $t + 1$. The standard algorithm used for global model aggregation, FedAvg [35], is provably not robust against poisoning attacks. For this reason, we propose the devised ContrAvg algorithm for constructing the global model \mathbf{w}^{t+1} of FL round $t + 1$ as follows

$$\mathbf{w}^{t+1} = \sum_{i \in S^t} a_i \mathbf{w}_i^t \quad (10)$$

The pseudocode detailing the steps to calculate the contribution index $a_i, \forall i \in S^t$ and to produce the global model using ContrAvg is presented in Algorithm 1. The overall complexity of Algorithm 1 is $\mathcal{O}(S^t)$.

B. CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS OF CONTRAVG

In this section, we enclose a theoretical analysis of the impact of using the proposed Shapley-inspired index to weigh the different nodes' local model updates on the convergence rate of the overall FL process. It should be noted that the convergence analysis indirectly considers the impact of jamming attacks by accounting for the subset of edge nodes S whose local model updates are successfully decoded and included in the global model calculation.

Let $F(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \alpha_i F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i)$ be the global loss function of the FL process. Following previous works [22], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40], we make the following assumptions about the properties of F and gradient estimations.

Assumption 1 (L-Smooth): The global loss function $F(\mathbf{w})$ is L -smooth with constant $L > 0$, such that

$$F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1}) - F(\mathbf{w}^t) \leq \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)^\top (\mathbf{w}^{t+1} - \mathbf{w}^t) + \frac{L}{2} \|\mathbf{w}^{t+1} - \mathbf{w}^t\|^2, \forall t. \quad (11)$$

By expressing $F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1})$ using the second-order Taylor expansion implies that the first gradient of the loss function ∇F is uniformly Lipschitz continuous with respect to \mathbf{w}^t for every communication round t .

Assumption 2 (μ -Strongly Convex): The global loss function $F(\mathbf{w})$ is μ -strongly convex with parameter $\mu > 0$, such that

$$F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1}) - F(\mathbf{w}^t) \geq \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)^\top (\mathbf{w}^{t+1} - \mathbf{w}^t) + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\mathbf{w}^{t+1} - \mathbf{w}^t\|^2, \forall t. \quad (12)$$

Assumption 3 (Twice Continuously Differentiable): The global loss function $F(\mathbf{w})$ is twice-continuously differentiable. Hence, based on (11) and (12), it holds that

$$\mu I \leq \nabla^2 F(\mathbf{w}^t) \leq LI. \quad (13)$$

Assumption 4: Given $\rho_1, \rho_2 \in \mathbb{R}^+$, the following condition holds true

$$\|\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_j, y_j, \mathbf{w}_i^t)\|^2 \leq \rho_1 + \rho_2 \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2. \quad (14)$$

Assumptions 1-4 are satisfied by several commonly used loss functions, including the cross-entropy loss function considered in this paper. Therefore, the expected convergence rate of the FL process employing the proposed ContrAvg algorithm is concluded in Theorem 1.

Theorem 1: Suppose that Assumptions 1-4 are satisfied, and let η represent the learning rate of the SGD method and \mathbf{w}^* the optimal global model, then the upper bound of $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1})] - \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^*)]$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1})] - \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^*)] &\leq \prod_{i=1}^{t+1} \gamma \cdot \mathbb{E}\left[(F(\mathbf{w}^0) - F(\mathbf{w}^*))\right] \\ &+ 2\eta \left[\frac{\rho_1}{1 - \rho_2} + 3\lambda \left(\rho_1 + \frac{\rho_1 \rho_2}{1 - \rho_2} \right) \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{1}{D_i} \right) \right] \frac{1 - \prod_{i=1}^t \gamma}{1 - \gamma}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\gamma = 1 - \eta\mu$ and λ the number of local iterations.

Proof: See the Appendix. ■

In Theorem 1, \mathbf{w}^{t+1} is the global model obtained using only the local models of all nodes $i \in \mathcal{S}^t$ whose messages are successfully decoded, weighted by the devised Shapley-inspired index. On the contrary, \mathbf{w}^* is the optimal global model derived from the local models of all nodes $i \in \mathcal{I}$ under the ideal scenario with no jamming attacks using ContrAvg. From Theorem 1, it is observed that the optimality

Algorithm 1 Contribution Averaging (ContrAvg)

Require: $\kappa_1, \kappa_2, \mathcal{S}^t, D_i, \forall i$

Ensure: Aggregated global model \mathbf{w}^{t+1} .

```

1: for each FL round  $t$  do
2:   /* Local Model Calculation */
3:   Successfully obtain local model  $\mathbf{w}_i^t, \forall i \in \mathcal{S}^t$ .
4:   for  $k = 1 : 1 : \mathcal{S}^t$  do
5:      $\mathcal{C}_k = \mathcal{S}^t - \{k\}$ 
6:      $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{\mathcal{C}_k}^t \leftarrow \sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}_k} \frac{D_i}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{C}_k} D_j} \mathbf{w}_i^t$ 
7:   end for
8:   /* Contribution Index Calculation */
9:   for each node  $i \in \mathcal{S}^t$  do
10:     $\phi_i^t = \kappa_1 \cdot \left( Q(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{\mathcal{S}^t}^t) - Q(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{\mathcal{S}^t - \{i\}}^t) \right) + \kappa_2 \cdot \left( Q(\mathbf{w}_i^t) - Q(\mathbf{w}^{t-1}) \right)$ 
11:     $a_i \leftarrow \frac{e^{\phi_i^t}}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}^t} e^{\phi_j^t}}$  // Apply softmax
12:   end for
13:   /* Global Model Calculation */
14:    $\mathbf{w}^{t+1} \leftarrow \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}^t} a_i \mathbf{w}_i^t$ 
15: end for

```

gap between $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1})]$ and $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^*)]$ remains bounded by a factor that decays exponentially with t controlled by $\gamma = 1 - \eta\mu < 1$. Despite the loss of information from nodes whose messages are not successfully decoded due to jamming attacks, the model's deviation from the optimal solution \mathbf{w}^* is finite, and convergence is achieved. The upper bound is a function of parameters related to the convexity properties of the global loss function (i.e., ρ_1, ρ_2), the number of local model iterations γ , the learning rate η , and the size of nodes' dataset $D_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$.

IV. ANTI-JAMMING POWER CONTROL IN WIRELESS FL NETWORKS: A BAYESIAN GAME APPROACH

This section introduces a distributed power control solution for jamming attack mitigation, in which both legitimate and malicious nodes autonomously determine their uplink transmission powers in each communication round t . The power control problem is formulated and solved as a Bayesian game with incomplete information, based on each node's belief about the type (i.e., malicious or legitimate) of the other nodes in the network. First, the malicious-aware utility is defined for each node along with the formula to estimate the maliciousness probability of others in the game. Subsequently, the Bayesian game with incomplete information is formally defined along with the concluded Bayesian Nash Equilibrium (BNE) solution concept. For simplicity in the notation, the index t is omitted in the rest of this section.

A. MALICIOUS-AWARE UTILITY MODEL

Each node $i \in \mathcal{I}$ has a utility function U_i which captures its satisfaction and incurred costs from participating in the FL

FIGURE 2. Maliciousness probability estimation by node i concerning node j , with $\xi = 0.03$ and $\delta = 20$.

process, defined as follows

$$U_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}) = \mathbb{1}_{\{p_i^{thr} \leq p_{max}\}} \cdot \left(c_1 a_i + c_2 \frac{T - T_i}{T} - c_3 p_i \right), \quad (16)$$

where $c_1, c_2, c_3, T \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are scalar constants for normalization and weighting between the variables a_i, T_i, p_i . The term $\mathbb{1}_{\{p_i^{thr} \leq p_{max}\}}$ implies that node i obtains non-zero utility when its minimum required transmission power p_i^{thr} is less than or equal to its maximum power budget p_{max} , which is the case that its message is successfully transmitted. Defining the utility as a linear combination of each node's i transmission time T_i and power p_i effectively captures the nodes' goal of prompt model transmission with minimal power consumption. The addition of the contribution index a_i in Eq. (16) further reflects the positive reward allocated by the server to each node. Hence, a node's satisfaction increases with its contribution a_i , and with a decrease in the transmission time T_i and power p_i overheads.

To incorporate both legitimate and malicious behavior into the nodes' utility function, we introduce a modified utility $V_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, which is defined as a convex combination of the different nodes' utilities

$$V_i = U_i + \theta_i \sum_{i \neq j} U_j, \quad (17)$$

where $\theta_i \in [-1, 0]$ characterizes the type of each node $i \in \mathcal{I}$ concerning their involvement in jamming attacks. Specifically, $\theta_i = 0$ indicates a legitimate node, whereas $\theta_i < 0$ indicates a malicious node that seeks to maximize its utility U_i while minimizing the utilities of the rest of the nodes. In the general case, there can also be scenarios where $\theta_i > 0$, indicating that node i is selfless and takes into account the utilities of other nodes. However, this cooperative setting is beyond the scope of this paper.

B. MALICIOUSNESS PROBABILITY

In this paper, the proposed anti-jamming power control solution relies on Bayesian games to account for the uncertainty of each node regarding the types of malice of other nodes. To make informed decisions about their uplink transmission powers during the game, each node i

estimates the conditional probability distribution of the types of other nodes given its type. In the following, we describe the formula used by a node i to estimate the conditional probability $Pr[\theta_j = 0 | \theta_i]$ of node j being legitimate ($\theta = 0$) given that node i is of type θ_i .

Specifically, each node i estimates the conditional probability $Pr[\theta_j = 0 | \theta_i]$ by comparing its contribution index a_i to the contribution index a_j of node j . This comparison assumes that the coordinating server has broadcast this information to all nodes participating in the game, which is a common rationality assumption in game theory. Given the latter assumption, the probability $Pr[\theta_j = 0 | \theta_i]$ is derived as follows

$$Pr[\theta_j = 0 | \theta_i] = f\left(\zeta \cdot \frac{a_j - a_i}{\max(\mathbf{a}) - \min(\mathbf{a})}, \pm \xi\right) \quad (18)$$

where $f(x, \pm \xi)$ is the sigmoid tangent function used to scale the probabilities within $[0, 1]$, with $x = \zeta \cdot \frac{a_j - a_i}{\max(\mathbf{a}) - \min(\mathbf{a})}$, $\zeta \in \mathbb{R}^+$. The input $x = \frac{a_j - a_i}{\max(\mathbf{a}) - \min(\mathbf{a})}$ of function $f(x, \pm \xi)$ corresponds to the normalized difference between a_j and a_i , scaled by the total range of values of the contribution indices vector \mathbf{a} . The normalization ensures that the probability calculation remains robust to variations in the spread of contribution indices, even in scenarios with a limited number of nodes due to external factors like jamming. Furthermore, the function $f(x, \pm \xi)$ takes as input a small positive constant parameter $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^+$ to control the horizontal shift of the curve. The analytic definition of the sigmoid tangent function is provided below

$$f(x, \xi) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{e^{\delta(x+\xi)} - e^{-\delta(x+\xi)}}{e^{\delta(x+\xi)} + e^{-\delta(x+\xi)}} + 1 \right), \quad (19)$$

where $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is a constant that controls the steepness of the curve.

The operation and interpretation of (18) and of the estimated conditional probability $Pr[\theta_j = 0 | \theta_i]$ is illustrated in Fig. 2. Consider a malicious node i as an example. The malicious node i engaged in poisoning attacks has a lower contribution index a_i compared to a legitimate node j with index a_j . By knowing its own type θ_i and comparing its contribution index a_j against a_i , node i can estimate the probability that node j is either malicious or legitimate. The horizontal shift parameter ξ of the sigmoid function adjusts this estimation, assigning lower probabilities to nodes with equal or lower a_j values than a_i and higher probabilities to nodes with significantly greater a_j values than a_i (red curve in Fig. 2). Similarly, the green curve in Fig. 2 shows the behavior of estimating maliciousness probabilities from a selfless node's perspective, where $\xi > 0$. This indicates a similar behavior but extends the current work to cooperative scenarios among nodes, which is beyond the scope of this paper.

C. BAYESIAN GAME WITH INCOMPLETE INFORMATION

In each communication round, the interactions among the nodes are captured by a Bayesian game with incomplete information, which is described by the tuple $\mathcal{G} = \{\mathcal{I}, \Theta, \mathcal{P}, \Psi, \mathcal{V}\}$, including the following elements:

- A set of players, i.e., edge nodes, $\mathcal{I} = \mathcal{N} \cup \mathcal{M}$.
- A set of types $\Theta_i = \{\theta_i \in [-1, 0]\}$ for each node i , resulting in a total type set $\Theta = \Theta_1 \times \dots \times \Theta_i \times \dots \times \Theta_{N+M}$ for game \mathcal{G} .
- A set of actions $\mathcal{P}_i = \{p_i \in [0, p_{max}]\}$ available to each node i , resulting in a total action set $\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{P}_1 \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}_i \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}_{N+M}$ for game \mathcal{G} .
- A set of probabilities $\Psi_i = Pr\{\theta_i \in [-1, 0]\}$ capturing the belief of node i about the other nodes' types, resulting in the joint probability set $\Psi = \Psi_1 \times \dots \times \Psi_i \times \dots \times \Psi_{N+M}$ for the game \mathcal{G} .
- A set of utility functions $\mathcal{V} = \{V_1, \dots, V_i, \dots, V_{N+M}\}$ of the participating nodes in the game \mathcal{G} .

The Bayesian game is treated as a distributed utility maximization problem, where each node i seeks to maximize its expected modified utility $\mathbb{E}[V_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i})]$ based on the conditional probability of the other nodes' types given its type. The optimization problem to be solved by each node is

$$\max_{p_i \in \mathcal{P}_i} U_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}) + \theta_i \sum_{i \neq j} U_j(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}) \cdot Pr[\theta_j = 0 | \theta_i] \quad (20a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } p_i \geq p_i^{thr}, \quad (20b)$$

where $Pr[\theta_j = 0 | \theta_i]$ is the probability that node j is legitimate, as estimated by node i of type θ_i .

The solution of the formulated game \mathcal{G} is a Bayesian Nash Equilibrium (BNE), which is concluded by implementing a typical Best Response Dynamics (BRD) algorithm [29].

Definition 1: Bayesian Nash Equilibrium (BNE) The action profile $\{p_i^*, \mathbf{p}_{-i}^*\}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$ is a BNE, if $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$ and $\forall p_i \in \mathcal{P}_i$ and $\mathbf{p}_{-i} \in \mathcal{P}_{-i}$ it holds true that

$$\mathbb{E}[V_i(p_i^*, \mathbf{p}_{-i}^*)] \geq \mathbb{E}[V_i(p_i, \mathbf{p}_{-i}^*)]. \quad (21)$$

Definition 1 implies that, at the BNE, no player can benefit from unilaterally changing its action. The following theorem proves the existence of at least one BNE point for game \mathcal{G} .

Theorem 2: Existence of BNE The Bayesian game \mathcal{G} admits at least one BNE iff (i) the action set \mathcal{P}_i is convex, compact, and nonempty $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, (ii) the utility function V_i is continuous in both p_i and \mathbf{p}_{-i} $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, (iii) the utility function V_i is concave in p_i for any \mathbf{p}_{-i} $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$.

Proof: The satisfaction of conditions (i) and (ii) can be easily verified. To verify condition (iii), the concavity of the node's utility U_i is first analyzed. By performing basic mathematical operations, the second derivative of U_i with respect to p_i is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 U_i}{dp_i^2} &= -\frac{2c_2}{T} \frac{Z(\mathbf{w}_i) \log(2)}{B \log^3(1 + \frac{G_i p_i}{I_i + I_0})} \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{G_i p_i}{I_i + I_0})^2} \frac{G_i^2}{(I_i + I_0)^2} \\ &\quad - \frac{c_2}{T} \frac{Z(\mathbf{w}_i) \log(2)}{B \log^2(1 + \frac{G_i p_i}{I_i + I_0})} \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{G_i p_i}{I_i + I_0})^2} \frac{G_i^2}{(I_i + I_0)^2}, \end{aligned}$$

where $I_i = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} G_j p_j$. Given that all constants and variables are positively defined, it holds that $\frac{d^2 U_i}{dp_i^2} < 0$ and thus U_i is a concave function.

For the modified utility function V_i to be concave in p_i , as the sum of concave functions U_i , the following condition must be satisfied for each node type parameter θ_i

$$\frac{d^2 U_i}{dp_i^2} + \theta_i \sum_{j \neq i} \frac{d^2 U_j}{dp_i^2} \leq 0, \quad \theta_i \in [-1, 0], \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}. \quad (22)$$

This completes the proof. \blacksquare

V. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed unified approach and each individual mechanism via modeling and simulation. The simulation settings and parameters are initialized as follows. We consider a wireless FL network arranged within a 500×500 square area. The server is located at the center of the area, whereas $I = 5$ nodes are uniformly distributed. One node is classified as malicious ($M = 1$) with $\theta_1 = -0.17$, while the rest $N = 4$ are legitimate nodes with $\theta_i = 0, \forall i \in \{2, \dots, 5\}$. The channel gain between the nodes and the server is calculated based on the distance-based path loss model given by $PL = 128.1 + 37.6 \log_{10}(d)$, where d [km] is the Euclidean distance between them [41]. It is assumed that the nodes are arranged and indexed ($i = 1, \dots, 5$) in an ascending order based on their channel gain, such that the node with the lowest channel gain ($i = 1$) is malicious. Following the principles of NOMA used for uplink local model transmissions, this arrangement allows the malicious node to negatively impact the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) of legitimate nodes, thus increasing their susceptibility to jamming attacks. The rest of the simulation-related parameters are set as $B = 20$ MHz, $I_0 = -174$ dBm/Hz, $p_{max} = 1$ W, $p_{tol} = -94$ dBm, $T = 0.1$ sec, and $Z(\mathbf{w}_i) = 1.5$ Mbits, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$ [41], $\kappa_1 = \kappa_2 = 2$. Also, the constants $c_1 = 2$, $c_2 = 1$, $c_3 = 2$, $\zeta = 0.1$, and $\xi = 0.03$ were carefully selected after thorough experimentation to accurately reflect the nodes' objectives in their utility function and minimize the system's transmission time and power.

The FL model is trained on the MNIST dataset [42], unless otherwise explicitly stated, which contains 60,000 samples equally distributed among nodes and in a non-IID manner, such that each node possesses samples from approximately two labels. The larger and more complex CIFAR10 dataset [43] is also adopted to enhance the validity and applicability of the ContrAvg algorithm to more challenging and realistic tasks within the FL framework. The wide adoption of the MNIST and CIFAR10 datasets [44] allows direct comparison and reproducibility with other works in the literature. The focus is intentionally placed on non-IID data due to the increased complexity, particularly in cross-silo FL environments where such distributions are more realistic [15]. To implement the non-IID setting in both datasets, all data samples are first sorted in ascending order based on their labels. Then, the sorted dataset is evenly partitioned among all nodes. This ensures that all nodes contribute to the global model, exacerbating the

FIGURE 3. Proposed Shapley value-inspired contribution index a_i of malicious and legitimate nodes (a) under different types of poisoning attacks and data distributions, and (b) compared against the original Shapley value index.

impact of jamming attacks on global model accuracy. The training is performed over 50 epochs, including $\lambda = 2$ local model updates with learning rate $\eta = 0.001$. As far as the MNIST dataset is concerned, each node’s local model uses a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for image classification, featuring a Conv2D layer with 32 filters, a MaxPooling2D layer, two Dense layers with 256 and 128 units, and Dropout layers. The final output layer consists of 10 units with a softmax activation. For the CIFAR10 dataset, the designed CNN consists of three convolutional blocks. Each block contains two Conv2D layers with 32, 64, and 128 filters, respectively, followed by Batch Normalization, a MaxPooling2D layer, and a Dropout layer with a 25% rate to prevent overfitting. After flattening the extracted features, the model includes a Dense layer with 128 units and ReLU activation, followed by another Dropout layer. The final output layer consists of 10 units with a softmax activation to classify images into the CIFAR10 categories. All experiments were conducted on an NVIDIA Tesla T4 with 16GB of memory.

In all experiments, we apply the proposed Bayesian game with incomplete information and the ContrAvg algorithm, unless otherwise explicitly stated. By default, the malicious user launches both jamming and poisoning attacks, except in some scenarios where the effects of jamming and poisoning are studied separately. The numerical results presented in the remainder of this section have been averaged over five independent FL executions, minimizing randomness effects inherent in machine learning models.

A. EVALUATION OF CONTRAVG ALGORITHM

This section examines the ContrAvg algorithm’s operation and its effectiveness in detecting and mitigating poisoning attacks in the FL network. First, the algorithm’s robustness against poisoning attacks is assessed by considering various data distributions (i.e., IID and non-IID), and different types of poisoning attacks. Specifically, three distinct categories of attacks are considered: (i) “Label Flipping”, the default

poisoning attack through Section V, in which the malicious node alters all the labels of its samples deterministically, (ii) “Random Label Flipping”, in which the labels of data samples are randomly altered by the malicious node, and (iii) “Model Poisoning”, wherein the malicious node introduces Gaussian noise $\mathcal{N} \sim (0, 0.15)$ to the model parameters. Fig. 3(a) shows the contribution index a_i of the malicious node compared to the mean value of legitimate nodes under the two types of attacks, considering both IID and non-IID data distributions. It is observed that when the malicious node does not engage in poisoning attacks, its contribution index closely matches that of other nodes, indicating a fair contribution to the aggregated global model. However, executing any type of poisoning attack results in a significant decrease in its a_i , reducing its contribution to the global model and facilitating its detection by the proposed ContrAvg algorithm. Concerning the different distributions, in the IID case, the disparity between the malicious and the legitimate nodes is slightly greater, as expected, but not substantial, showing the ContrAvg algorithm’s robustness in mitigating adversarial influence, regardless of data distribution.

Secondly, the performance of the proposed Shapley-inspired contribution index (termed “Our Contr. Index”) is compared against the original Shapley value in terms of its effectiveness in detecting malicious nodes and computational efficiency. Fig. 3(b) presents the contribution index of the nodes in this context for both “Our Contr. Index” and “Shapley” approaches, under conditions with and without poisoning attacks. Notably, our approach exhibits comparable effectiveness with the original Shapley value under both no-attack and attack cases, despite being of linear computational complexity $\mathcal{O}(S^l)$ compared to $\mathcal{O}(2^{S^l})$ of the original Shapley value, where S^l is the number of nodes who successfully transmit their local model updates. The latter is corroborated by the real execution times presented in Table 1 for both approaches and datasets. In detail, our contribution index calculation results in an approximately 2.3 times faster execution with the MNIST dataset and 1.9 times with the

TABLE 1. Real execution time comparison between the original Shapley value and our proposed contribution index.

Scenario	1 FL Round	Total FL Time
Shapley MNIST	354 s	17702 s
Our Contr. Index MNIST	155 s	7781 s
Shapley CIFAR10	654 s	32746 s
Our Contr. Index CIFAR10	355 s	17801 s

TABLE 2. Accuracy of the aggregated global model after FL convergence, under different FL averaging methods.

Aggregation Method	Mean Accuracy	Mean Accuracy
	MNIST	CIFAR10
ContrAvg	81.1 %	45.3 %
FedAvg	76.4 %	41.3 %
Median Avg	75.4 %	37.2 %
Shapley ContrAvg	79.7 %	46.8 %
Trimmed Mean Avg	72.8 %	45.3 %

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 4. Accuracy of the aggregated global model over FL epochs, under different FL averaging methods, for the (a) MNIST and (b) CIFAR10 datasets.

CIFAR10 dataset compared to the original Shapley, rendering our approach more practical for large-scale FL networks.

Finally, the ContrAvg algorithm is assessed against alternative state-of-the-art aggregation algorithms, concerning the achieved accuracy of the global FL model. Specifically, the following benchmark scenarios are considered: (i) “Shapley ContrAvg”: The same algorithm is employed as in our “ContrAvg” case, but with the original Shapley value utilized, (ii) “FedAvg” [35], (iii) Coordinate-wise “Median Avg” [17]: The server aggregates the model weights by calculating their medians, and (iv) Coordinate-wise “Trimmed Mean Avg” [17]: The model updates are sorted in ascending order and the lower and upper 25% are discarded before calculating the mean. Fig. 4 depicts the variation in the global model’s accuracy as a function of the training epochs for both the proposed approach and the comparative

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 5. Convergence analysis of the (a) malicious node’s transmission power (b) global model’s accuracy, under different comparative scenarios, for the MNIST dataset.

scenarios, for the (a) MNIST and (b) CIFAR10 datasets. The concluding accuracy values for each scenario after the convergence of the FL process are also summarized in Table 2, highlighting the performance at the end of the training process.

Regarding the MNIST dataset, Fig. 4(a) shows that the ContrAvg algorithm outperforms all other comparative scenarios. Supporting the findings in Fig. 3(b), our ContrAvg algorithm has comparable or superior accuracy to the non-polynomial “Shapley ContrAvg” scenario. In contrast, the accuracy of the other three benchmark scenarios declines significantly compared to the proposed ContrAvg. It should be noted that achieving accuracy significantly beyond 80% is nearly impossible in this simulation setup due to the

FIGURE 6. Scalability analysis of the mean nodes' (a) transmission power, (b) time overhead, and (c) energy overhead, under different comparative scenarios.

non-IID nature of the data. The malicious node controls roughly 2 of the 10 MNIST labels and launches label-flipping attacks, leading the aggregated model to misclassify these labels. This results in a consistent classification error of approximately 20%, underscoring the robust performance of ContrAvg. The effectiveness of advanced model aggregation methods, such as the original “Shapley ContrAvg” and our proposed ContrAvg, on the achieved accuracy, is more clearly demonstrated when using more complex datasets such as the CIFAR10. As illustrated in Fig. 4(b), these aggregation methods achieve the highest accuracy while remaining stable across the FL epochs. Contrariwise, “Median Avg” and “Trimmed Mean Avg” exhibit severe fluctuations due to the inefficient detection of the poisoned model updates. Therefore, although the “Trimmed Mean Avg” appears to achieve equal accuracy to the ContrAvg in the last FL epoch (see Table 2), this result is inconsistent, varying by approximately 10% between consecutive epochs. Also, although “FedAvg” has a similarly stable performance as the contribution averaging methods, the latter outperforms it by achieving over 10% improvement in the accuracy.

B. EVALUATION OF BAYESIAN-BASED POWER CONTROL

In this section, we focus on the performance evaluation of the proposed anti-jamming power control solution based on Bayesian games with incomplete information, subsequently referred to as “Incomplete Bayesian”. To this end, the following comparative scenarios are considered: (i) “No jamming”: All nodes are treated as legitimate, i.e., $\theta_i = 0, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, and no jamming attack occurs in the FL network, which does not imply the lack of poisoning attacks by the malicious node; (ii) “Complete Bayesian”: All nodes possess complete information regarding the type of the other nodes and the probabilities are determined by $Pr[\theta_j = 0] = 1, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}$ and $Pr[\theta_j = 0] = 0, \forall j \in \mathcal{M}$; (iii) “Stackelberg”: The interactions among the nodes are modeled as a Stackelberg game, where the malicious node acts as the leader and the legitimate nodes serve as followers, considering the same utility functions with the proposed Bayesian game with complete information; and (iv) “ $P_{thres} + \Delta p$ ”: All nodes transmit their local model parameters with transmission

power P_{thres} increased by Δp for their signals to be decodable. For the legitimate clients, $\Delta p = 0.05$ W is fixed, whereas for the malicious client Δp is a randomly distributed variable $\Delta p \sim \mathcal{N}(0.1, 0.1)$.

Fig. 5 studies the convergence of the malicious node’s transmission power (Fig. 5(a)) and the global model’s accuracy (Fig. 5(b)) under the different comparative scenarios. Specifically, Fig. 5(a) showcases that in all scenarios except for the “ $P_{thres} + \Delta p$ ”, the power of the malicious node converges, signifying the effective mitigation of the jamming attacks. The sole exception arises in the “ $P_{thres} + \Delta p$ ” scenario, where the absence of an intelligent power control strategy allows the malicious node to fluctuate its power levels. Specifically, each spike in the malicious node’s power indicates a jamming attempt during the respective FL round. Notably, the “Complete Bayesian” scenario shows a higher attack frequency compared to our incomplete information approach, as the malicious node, knowing other nodes’ types, is more motivated to disrupt their transmissions. In contrast, under the “Incomplete Bayesian” scenario, the malicious node must estimate the type of each node, creating uncertainty about the effectiveness of its attacks, thereby reducing their frequency. Last, in the “Stackelberg” scenario, where the malicious node announces its power level to the legitimate nodes, the legitimate nodes seem to adapt their power levels to counteract the attacks. Consequently, the malicious node’s attack attempts, while present, are largely ineffective due to insufficient power to disrupt the other node successfully. It is remarkable that, despite the absence of successful attacks in this case, this approach leads to considerably higher transmission power compared to the proposed method. In fact, once equilibrium is attained power aligns with that of the “Complete Bayesian” scenario.

Similar trends can be observed in Fig. 5(b) for the global model accuracy across the different scenarios and over the FL epochs. As the frequency of jamming attacks increases, the global model accuracy deteriorates. The proposed “Incomplete Bayesian” scenario achieves the second-highest accuracy, closely matching the ideal “No Jamming Bayesian Game” scenario, where no attacks occur in the FL network. On the contrary, the frequent attacks in the “Complete Bayesian” scenario lead to a sharp drop in accuracy, as many

nodes fail to transmit their local models due to interference. Expectedly, the “ $P_{thres} + \Delta_p$ ” method yields the lowest accuracy due to continuous jamming throughout the FL rounds.

Finally, a scalability analysis is conducted to showcase the impact of increasing the number of nodes in the FL network. Since the NOMA technique is used to multiplex the nodes’ transmissions, resulting in interference among them, this analysis considers NOMA clusters 2 to 5 nodes, aligning with common practices in the literature. In case more nodes are added to the network, the nodes will be grouped into separate NOMA clusters operating on different frequency bands, and the proposed anti-jamming power control solution will be applied independently to each cluster. Figs. 6(a)-6(c) present the mean transmission power, time, and energy consumption of the nodes, respectively. In all comparative scenarios, an increase in the number of nodes leads to higher mean transmission power due to increased interference experienced by nodes sharing the same frequency resources. This, in turn, results in an increase in both the transmission time and the energy consumed. In terms of comparative performance, the proposed “Incomplete Bayesian” and “Stackelberg” scenarios consistently outperform the other two scenarios across all examined metrics, closely aligning with the ideal “No Jamming” scenario.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we tackled the problem of coordinated jamming and poisoning attacks in wireless FL networks by proposing a unified framework that integrates two complementary mechanisms, each targeting a specific type of attack. First, we introduced a robust global model aggregation algorithm designed to mitigate poisoning attacks by leveraging contribution indices to appropriately weigh each edge node’s impact on the global model. These indices are computed using a Shapley-inspired formula, which, contrary to the original Shapley value, exhibits polynomial computational complexity. Furthermore, an anti-jamming mechanism to control the transmission power levels of the nodes was designed based on a Bayesian game with incomplete information among the legitimate and malicious nodes. Both legitimate and malicious nodes autonomously determine their uplink transmission powers given their belief about the type (i.e., malicious or legitimate) of the other nodes. The unified framework and each individual mechanism were evaluated in terms of their performance and efficiency via modeling and simulation. Comparisons against state-of-the-art solutions against jamming and poisoning attacks demonstrated the superiority of the unified framework in achieving a good tradeoff between global model accuracy and consumed transmission power and time.

Our current and future work focuses on jointly addressing jamming and poisoning attacks in wireless FL networks while exploring cooperative scenarios, where nodes may consider the utilities of others when playing a game. Moreover, studying coordinated eavesdropping and poisoning attacks

is of interest, which again is an unexplored domain in the literature around wireless FL.

APPENDIX PROOF OF THEOREM 1

Based on the Assumptions 1-4, the update of the global model in the $(t+1)$ th FL round can be expressed as a function of the global model in the t th FL round as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{w}^{t+1} &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}^t} \alpha_i \left(\mathbf{w}^t - \eta \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda-1} \nabla F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l}) \right) \Leftrightarrow \\ \mathbf{w}^{t+1} &= \mathbf{w}^t \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}^t} \alpha_i - \eta \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}^t} \alpha_i \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda-1} \nabla F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l}) \Leftrightarrow \\ \mathbf{w}^{t+1} &= \mathbf{w}^t - \eta (\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t) - \mathbf{e}^t), \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where we utilize the property that $\sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}^t} \alpha_i = 1$ that holds for the contribution indices, as analyzed in Section III-A. Also, we define \mathbf{e}^t as $\mathbf{e}^t = \mathbf{e}_1^t + \mathbf{e}_2^t$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_1^t &= \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t) - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \alpha_i \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda-1} \nabla F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l}), \\ \mathbf{e}_2^t &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \alpha_i \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda-1} \nabla F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l}) - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}^t} \alpha_i \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda-1} \nabla F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l}). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Based on (23) and Assumption 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1}) &\leq F(\mathbf{w}^t) + \left(\frac{L\eta^2}{2} - \eta \right) \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 + \frac{L\eta^2}{2} \|\mathbf{e}^t\|^2 \\ &\quad + \eta(1 - L\eta) \langle \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t), \mathbf{e}^t \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where for $\langle \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t), \mathbf{e}^t \rangle$, we use the identity $xy \leq \frac{1}{2}(x^2 + y^2)$, with $x = \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)$ and $y = \mathbf{e}^t$. Immediately, (25) transforms as follows

$$\begin{aligned} F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1}) &\leq F(\mathbf{w}^t) + \left(\frac{L\eta^2}{2} - \eta \right) \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 + \frac{L\eta^2}{2} \|\mathbf{e}^t\|^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{\eta}{2} (1 - L\eta) \left(\|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 + \|\mathbf{e}^t\|^2 \right) \Leftrightarrow \\ F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1}) &\leq F(\mathbf{w}^t) - \frac{\eta}{2} \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 + \frac{\eta}{2} \|\mathbf{e}^t\|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Given that all elements in (26) are positive, the inequality expression in (26) remains the same for the case of estimated mean values. Thus, (26) can be approximated as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1})] &\leq \mathbb{E}\left[F(\mathbf{w}^t) - \frac{\eta}{2} \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 + \frac{\eta}{2} \|\mathbf{e}^t\|^2 \right] \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{\leq} \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^t)] - \frac{\eta}{2} \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 + \eta \left(\|\mathbf{e}_1^t\|^2 + \|\mathbf{e}_2^t\|^2 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where for (a) consider $\|\mathbf{e}^t\|^2 \leq 2\|\mathbf{e}_1^t\|^2 + 2\|\mathbf{e}_2^t\|^2$.

To derive an upper bound for $\|\mathbf{e}_1^t\|^2$, we utilize the Assumption 4 and prove that

$$\|\mathbf{e}_1^t\|^2 = \left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t) - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \alpha_i \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda-1} \nabla F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l}) \right\|^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \left[\|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\| + \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \alpha_i \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda-1} \nabla F_i(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l}) \right\| \right]^2 \\
&\stackrel{(b)}{\leq} 2\|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 + 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda-1} \frac{1}{D_i^2} \sum_{j=1}^{D_i} \|\nabla f_i(\mathbf{x}_j, y_j, \mathbf{w}_i^{t,l})\|^2 \\
&\leq 2\|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 + 2\lambda \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 \right) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{1}{D_i},
\end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

with (b) deriving from Jensen Theorem and by utilizing $\alpha_i \leq 1$ and (a).

Similarly, to derive an upper bound for $\|\mathbf{e}_2^t\|^2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\mathbf{e}_2^t\|^2 &\leq 2\lambda \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 \right) \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{1}{D_i} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}^t} \frac{1}{D_i} \right) \\
&\leq 2\lambda \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 \right) \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{2}{D_i} \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Based on Assumption 4 and the definition of the global loss function, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\| &= \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\alpha_i}{D_i} \sum_{j=1}^{D_i} \nabla f(\mathbf{x}_j, y_j, \mathbf{w}_i^t) \right\| \stackrel{\text{triangle inequality}}{\leq} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\alpha_i}{D_i} \sum_{j=1}^{D_i} \|\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_j, y_j, \mathbf{w}_i^t)\| \\
&\stackrel{[\text{Assm 4}] \text{CS}, \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \alpha_i = 1}{\leq} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\alpha_i}{D_i} \sum_{j=1}^{D_i} \|\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_j, y_j, \mathbf{w}_i^t)\| \\
\|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 &\leq \rho_1 + \rho_2 \|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 \Leftrightarrow \\
\|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 &\leq \frac{\rho_1}{1 - \rho_2},
\end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

where Assm 4 refers to Assumption 4 and CS to the Cauchy-Schwarz Theorem. Also, consider $\rho_2 \in [0, 1)$.

From Assumptions 2 and 3, the Polyak-Lojasiewicz condition is satisfied with $\mu > 0$ as follows

$$\|\nabla F(\mathbf{w}^t)\|^2 \geq 2\mu(F(\mathbf{w}^t) - F(\mathbf{w}^*)), \tag{31}$$

By subtracting $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^*)]$ from both sides of (27) and utilizing (28)-(31), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1})] - \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^*)] \leq \gamma \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^t) - F(\mathbf{w}^*)] \\
&\quad + 2\eta \left[\frac{\rho_1}{1 - \rho_2} + 3\lambda \left(\rho_1 + \frac{\rho_1 \rho_2}{1 - \rho_2} \right) \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{1}{D_i} \right) \right],
\end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

where $\gamma = 1 - \eta\mu \leq 1$.

Finally, applying recursively inequality (32) to $t = 0$ gives

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^{t+1})] - \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^*)] \leq \prod_{i=1}^{t+1} \gamma \cdot \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}^0) - F(\mathbf{w}^*)] \\
&\quad + 2\eta \left[\frac{\rho_1}{1 - \rho_2} + 3\lambda \left(\rho_1 + \frac{\rho_1 \rho_2}{1 - \rho_2} \right) \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{1}{D_i} \right) \right] \frac{1 - \prod_{i=1}^t \gamma}{1 - \gamma},
\end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

which proves that convergence is achieved.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Liu et al., "Distributed intelligence in wireless networks," *IEEE Open J. Commun. Soc.*, vol. 4, pp. 1001–1039, 2023.
- [2] V. P. Chellapandi, L. Yuan, C. G. Brinton, S. H. Žak, and Z. Wang, "Federated learning for connected and automated vehicles: A survey of existing approaches and challenges," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Veh.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 119–137, Jan. 2024.
- [3] L. Zhao et al., "Adaptive multi-UAV trajectory planning leveraging digital twin technology for urban IIoT applications," *IEEE Trans. Netw. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 5349–5363, Nov/Dec. 2024.
- [4] L. Zhao, Y. Han, A. Hawbani, S. Wan, Z. Guo, and M. Guizani, "Media: An incremental DNN based computation offloading for collaborative cloud-edge computing," *IEEE Trans. Netw. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1986–1998, Mar./Apr. 2024.
- [5] A. Tariq et al., "Trustworthy federated learning: A comprehensive review, architecture, key challenges, and future research prospects," *IEEE Open J. Commun. Soc.*, vol. 5, pp. 4920–4998, 2024.
- [6] L. Zhao et al., "Generative abnormal data detection for enhancing cellular vehicle-to-everything-based road safety," *IEEE Trans. Green Commun. Netw.*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1466–1478, Dec. 2024.
- [7] E. Hallaji, R. Razavi-Far, M. Saif, B. Wang, and Q. Yang, "Decentralized federated learning: A survey on security and privacy," *IEEE Trans. Big Data*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 194–213, Apr. 2024.
- [8] Z. Wang, K. Huang, and Y. C. Eldar, "Spectrum breathing: Protecting over-the-air federated learning against interference," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 10058–10071, Aug. 2024.
- [9] Y. Cheriguene, W. Jaafar, H. Yanikomeroglu, and C. A. Kerrache, "Towards reliable participation in UAV-enabled federated edge learning on non-iid data," *IEEE Open J. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 5, pp. 125–141, 2024.
- [10] Z. Zhou et al., "MR-FFL: A stratified community-based mutual reliability framework for fairness-aware federated learning in heterogeneous UAV networks," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 11, no. 12, pp. 20995–21009, Jun. 2024.
- [11] N. M. Al-Maslamani, M. Abdallah, and B. S. Ciftler, "Reputation-aware multi-agent DRL for secure hierarchical federated learning in IoT," *IEEE Open J. Commun. Soc.*, vol. 4, pp. 1274–1284, 2023.
- [12] S. P. Sanon, R. Reddy, C. Lipps, and H. D. Schotten, "DDoS attacks in communication: Analysis and mitigation of unreliable clients in federated learning," in *Proc. IEEE 21st Consum. Commun. Netw. Conf. (CCNC)*, 2024, pp. 986–989.
- [13] M. Chen, Z. Yang, W. Saad, C. Yin, H. V. Poor, and S. Cui, "A joint learning and communications framework for federated learning over wireless networks," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 269–283, Jan. 2021.
- [14] W. Mao, X. Lu, Y. Jiang, and H. Zheng, "Joint client selection and bandwidth allocation of wireless federated learning by deep reinforcement learning," *IEEE Trans. Services Comput.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 336–348, Jan./Feb. 2024.
- [15] Y. Mao, Z. Ye, X. Yuan, and S. Zhong, "Secure model aggregation against poisoning attacks for cross-silo federated learning with robustness and fairness," *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Security*, vol. 19, pp. 6321–6336, 2024.
- [16] K. Pillutla, S. M. Kakade, and Z. Harchaoui, "Robust aggregation for federated learning," *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.*, vol. 70, pp. 1142–1154, 2022.
- [17] D. Yin, Y. Chen, R. Kannan, and P. Bartlett, "Byzantine-robust distributed learning: Towards optimal statistical rates," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Mach. Learn.*, 2018, pp. 5650–5659.
- [18] P. Blanchard, E. M. El Mhamdi, R. Guerraoui, and J. Stainer, "Machine learning with adversaries: Byzantine tolerant gradient descent," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 30, 2017, pp. 1–11.
- [19] S. Li, E. Ngai, and T. Voigt, "Byzantine-robust aggregation in federated learning empowered industrial IoT," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Informat.*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 1165–1175, Feb. 2023.
- [20] L. S. Shapley, "A value for n-person games," in *Contributions to the Theory of Games*, vol. 2. Princeton, NJ, USA: Princeton Univ. Press, 1953.
- [21] T. Song, Y. Tong, and S. Wei, "Profit allocation for federated learning," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Big Data (Big Data)*, 2019, pp. 2577–2586.
- [22] Q. Sun et al., "ShapleyFL: Robust federated learning based on Shapley value," in *Proc. 29th ACM SIGKDD Conf. Knowl. Disc. Data Min.*, 2023, pp. 2096–2108.

- [23] T. Wang, N. Huang, Y. Wu, and T. Q. S. Quek, "Energy-efficient wireless federated learning: A secrecy oriented design via sequential artificial jamming," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 72, no. 5, pp. 6412–6427, May 2023.
- [24] X. Hou, J. Wang, C. Jiang, X. Zhang, Y. Ren, and M. Debbah, "UAV-enabled covert federated learning," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 6793–6809, Oct. 2023.
- [25] Z. Tong, J. Wang, X. Hou, C. Jiang, and J. Liu, "UAV-assisted covert federated learning over mmWave massive MIMO," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 23, no. 9, pp. 11785–11798, Sep. 2024.
- [26] T. Wang, N. Huang, Y. Wu, J. Gao, and T. Q. S. Quek, "Latency-oriented secure wireless federated learning: A channel-sharing approach with artificial jamming," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 10, no. 11, pp. 9675–9689, Jun. 2023.
- [27] Y. Shi and Y. E. Sagduyu, "How to launch jamming attacks on federated learning in NextG wireless networks," in *Proc. IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, 2022, pp. 945–950.
- [28] Y. Shi, Y. E. Sagduyu, and T. Erpek, "Jamming attacks on decentralized federated learning in general multi-hop wireless networks," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Commun. Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [29] R. Ruby, H. Yang, and K. Wu, "Anti-jamming strategy for federated learning in Internet of Medical Things: A game approach," *IEEE J. Biomed. Health Inf.*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 888–899, Feb. 2023.
- [30] Y. Bi, Y. Wu, C. Hua, and F. Zou, "Evolutionary anti-jamming game in non-orthogonal multiple access system," in *Proc. IEEE Global Commun. Conf. (GLOBECOM)*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [31] C. Han, A. Liu, Z. Gao, K. An, G. Zheng, and S. Chatzinotas, "Anti-jamming transmission in NOMA-based satellite-enabled IoT: A game-theoretic framework in hostile environments," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 10, no. 23, pp. 20311–20322, Dec. 2023.
- [32] Y. Xu et al., "A one-leader multi-follower Bayesian-Stackelberg game for anti-jamming transmission in UAV communication networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 21697–21709, 2018.
- [33] Y. Li, K. Li, Z. Gao, and C. Zheng, "A multi-domain anti-jamming scheme based on Bayesian Stackelberg game with imperfect information," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 132250–132259, 2022.
- [34] H. Li, H. Yu, T. Rao, J. Shang, and F. Shen, "Effects of different loss functions on the classification performance of HybridSN networks," in *Proc. 3rd Int. Conf. Mach. Learn., Big Data Business Intell. (MLBDBI)*, 2021, pp. 500–503.
- [35] B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, S. Hampson, and B. A. y Arcas, "Communication-efficient learning of deep networks from decentralized data," in *Proc. Artif. Intell. Stat.*, 2017, pp. 1273–1282.
- [36] S. Zhang, Z. Yang, G. Chen, Z. Dong, and Z. Han, "Convergence analysis and energy minimization for reconfigurable intelligent surface-assisted federated learning," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 17384–17398, Nov. 2024.
- [37] Y. Zhao, Q. Wu, W. Chen, C. Wu, and H. V. Poor, "Performance-oriented design for intelligent reflecting surface-assisted federated learning," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 71, no. 9, pp. 5228–5243, Sep. 2023.
- [38] Z. Yang, M. Chen, W. Saad, C. S. Hong, and M. Shikh-Bahaei, "Energy efficient federated learning over wireless communication networks," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 1935–1949, Mar. 2021.
- [39] Y. Sun, S. Zhou, Z. Niu, and D. Gündüz, "Dynamic scheduling for over-the-air federated edge learning with energy constraints," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 227–242, Jan. 2022.
- [40] G. Zheng, Y. Fang, M. Wen, and Z. Ding, "Novel over-the-air federated learning via reconfigurable intelligent surface and SWIPT," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 11, no. 21, pp. 34140–34155, Nov. 2024.
- [41] P. Charatsaris, M. Diamanti, and S. Papavassiliou, "Joint user association and resource allocation for hierarchical federated learning based on games in satisfaction form," *IEEE Open J. Commun. Soc.*, vol. 5, pp. 457–471, 2024.
- [42] L. Deng, "The MNIST database of handwritten digit images for machine learning research [best of the Web]," *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.*, vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 141–142, Nov. 2012.
- [43] W. Cukierski. "Cifar-10—Object recognition in images." kaggle. 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://kaggle.com/competitions/cifar-10>
- [44] X. Ma, J. Zhu, Z. Lin, S. Chen, and Y. Qin, "A state-of-the-art survey on solving non-iid data in federated learning," *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 135, pp. 244–258, Oct. 2022.

SOFIA BARKATSA received the Diploma degree in electrical and computer engineering from the National Technical University of Athens, Greece, in 2024. She is currently pursuing the M.Sc. degree in cybersecurity with New York University. She is a Research Assistant with the Network Management and Optimal Design Laboratory, National Technical University of Athens. Her research interests lie in the area of security and AI-enabled next generation wireless networks.

MARIA DIAMANTI (Member, IEEE) received the Diploma degree in electrical and computer engineering from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, in 2018, and the Ph.D. degree from the National Technical University of Athens, Greece, in 2023, where she is a Postdoctoral Researcher with the Network Management and Optimal Design Laboratory. Her research interests lie in the area of resource optimization in 5G/6G wireless communication systems using game theory and reinforcement

learning techniques. She has been awarded the M. Stasinopoulos - VIOHALCO Foundation Best Ph.D. Thesis Award.

PANAGIOTIS CHARATSARIS (Graduate Student Member, IEEE) received the Diploma degree in electrical and computer engineering from the National Technical University of Athens, Greece, in 2021. He is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the National Technical University of Athens, where he is a Research Assistant with the Network Management and Optimal Design Laboratory. His research interests lie in the areas of 5G/6G wireless networks, resource management and optimization, game theory, and reinforcement learning.

STEFANOS VOIKOS received the Diploma degree in electrical and computer engineering from the National Technical University of Athens, Greece, in 2023. He is currently pursuing the M.Sc. degree in data science and machine learning with the National Technical University of Athens, where he is a Research Assistant with the Network Management and Optimal Design Laboratory. His research focuses on radio and compute resource allocation in wireless federated learning networks.

EIRINI ELENI TSIROPOULOU (Senior Member, IEEE) is currently an Associate Professor with the School of Electrical, Computer and Energy Engineering, Arizona State University, where she is the Director of the Performance and Resource Optimization in Networks – PROTON Lab. Her main research interests lie in the area of cyber-physical social systems and wireless heterogeneous networks, with an emphasis on network modeling and optimization, resource orchestration in interdependent systems, reinforcement learning,

game theory, network economics, and the Internet of Things. Four of her papers received the Best Paper Award at IEEE WCNC in 2012, ADHOCNETS in 2015, IEEE/IFIP WMNC 2019, and INFOCOM 2019 by the IEEE ComSoc Technical Committee on Communications Systems Integration and Modeling. She received the NSF CRII Award in 2019 and the Early Career Award from the IEEE Communications Society Internet Technical Committee in 2019. In 2017, she was selected by the IEEE Communication Society–N2Women—as one of the Top Ten Rising Stars in the communications and networking field.

SYMEON PAPAVALASSILIOU (Senior Member, IEEE) is currently a Professor with the School of ECE, National Technical University of Athens. From 1995 to 1999, he was a Senior Technical Staff Member with AT&T Laboratories, Middletown, NJ, USA. In August 1999, he joined the ECE Department, New Jersey Institute of Technology, USA, where he was an Associate Professor until 2004. He has an established record of publications in his field of expertise, with more than 400 technical journal and conference

published papers. His main research interests lie in the area of computer communication networks, with emphasis on the analysis, optimization, and performance evaluation of mobile and distributed systems, wireless networks, and complex systems. He received the Best Paper Award in IEEE INFOCOM 94, the AT&T Division Recognition and Achievement Award in 1997, the U.S. National Science Foundation Career Award in 2003, the Best Paper Award in IEEE WCNC 2012, the Excellence in Research Grant in Greece in 2012, the Best Paper Awards in ADHOCNETS 2015, ICT 2016, IEEE/IFIP WMNC 2019, and IEEE Globecom 2022, as well as the 2019 IEEE ComSoc Technical Committee on Communications Systems Integration and Modeling Best Paper Award (for his INFOCOM 2019 paper). He also served on the board of the Greek National Regulatory Authority on Telecommunications and Posts from 2006 to 2009.